

- 1) Wide field submm view of $z \sim 3$ protoclusters.
- 2) Candidate $z > 4$ mm-selected protoclusters in the South Pole Telescope survey

First Structures ; Sept 2023

Galaxy clusters are the building blocks of large scale structure

z=6

Millennium simulation

Progenitors of clusters – *Protoclusters*
– are traced in simulations

... and probed observationally, **sort of**
(how do we know an overdensity is a protocluster)

z=0

Massive Clusters detected out to z<2

2

2

The evolution of massive clusters

Can we find examples of massive clusters at different evolutionary stages?

Do simulations agree with our observations?

Expectation from Simulations: Protocluster Size

Muldrew et al. (2015)

Protoclusters are physically HUGE,
and the most massive progenitors
are the largest.

Volume collapses by a factor of
 ~ 100 between $z=3$ and $z=0.5$.

(Quantities measured related to protoclusters should
consider this volume transformation)

LOOKING ON \sim ARCMIN SCALES.

Chiang et al. (2013); see also Oñorbe et al. (2014)

Early *inside-out* formation in protocluster core (Chiang et al 2013,2017)

... SPT finding early
'cores' as
protocluster
signposts
*(prelude to our SPT-
protoclusters)*

Two recent case studies: bright *submm sources* in extended $\sim 30'$ -scale (30pMpc) protoclusters at $z \sim 3$

SSA22 $z=3.1$ (Chapman+ in prep)

HS1549 $z=2.9$ (Wang+ submitted)

Do bright ($S_{850} \sim 8$ mJy) SMGs trace the very extended collapsing structure of protoclusters?

Is this important for forming ellipticals in PCs?

$z=3.1$ SSA22 protocluster (Steidel+2000)

FIG. 1.—*Bottom right*: Sky map of the 283 candidate LAEs detected in Hayashino et al. (2004). The green line shows the average local surface density of LAEs in this field (see text). Cyan squares show two giant LABs. Blue circles show the field of view of six masks. Blue, green, and red points show the LAEs at $z = 3.05\text{--}3.08$, $3.08\text{--}3.10$, and $3.10\text{--}3.12$, respectively. The triangles show the LBGs in the SSA 22a field (red box; 8.7×8.9 ; Steidel et al. 2003). *Top right and bottom left*: Redshift-space distribution of 56 LAEs with spectroscopic redshifts. The red line shows the projected contour of the local volume density of LAEs of $2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ Mpc}^{-3}$ (see text). The predicted peculiar velocity dispersion of 400 km s^{-1} is shown by red arrows. The dotted lines show the redshift range sampled within $\geq 50\%$ of the peak transmittance of our narrowband filter.

Figure S1 | Schematic picture of this work. The filamentary structure in green shown in the top-left corner represents the proto-cluster outlined by Lyman- α emitting galaxies in the SSA 22 field. We found an apparent clustering of submillimetre galaxies, which are believed to be massive dusty starburst galaxies (orange dots; an artist's conception of a submillimetre galaxy is shown in the bottom-left corner), towards the proto-cluster using the AzTEC camera mounted on the ASTE telescope (shown in the bottom-right corner). Although the 1,100- μm map shows only the projected distribution of the submillimetre galaxies on the plane of the sky, it is likely that some fraction of our submillimetre galaxies actually belongs to the proto-cluster, marking the local peak of underlying mass distribution.

Wide field SCUBA2 followed up with NOEMA

Deep SCUBA2 850um map over 30' field (Geach+2018)

NOEMA followup of Brightest 25 SMGs (S850>7mJy)
-confirmed 3 central ones (in Umehata+18 ALMA map)
-found two outlying z=3.09 SMGs (not in LAE overdensity)

HS1549+19 $z=2.9$ protocluster (Steidel et al. 2011)

Ly α density map [h₇₀⁻¹cMpc]

Kikuta+2019

Protoclusters at $z > 3$ are large, $\sim 1 \text{ deg}^2$ region will collapse down by factor 100x

Looks like sims

$D[h^{-1} \text{ cMpc}]$

(Lacaille et al. 2017)

George Wang+ in prep

NOEMA followup of 25
SCUBA-2 sources with
 $S_{850} > 8 \text{ mJy}$
(20'x40' field)

18 are at $z \sim 2.85$ in PC
They lie in LAE region

**Severe contrast with
SSA22 protocluster!**

HS1549 vs SSA22

HS1549 SMGs/LAEs

SMGs 3d distribution
similar to LAE projected
distribution

Thin pancake structure
spanning 30x30x5 pMpc

HS1549 Phase space: Green highlights R_{Vir}

In multi-dark simulation:

Rare to have even 10
massive haloes within
HS1549 volume,
Let alone ~ 20 .

Lesson from wide field SMGs in protoclusters?

- Large variation in SMGs tracing extended 30' (30 pMpc) collapsing structure (between SSA22 and HS1549 at least)
- Bright SMGs are massive ellipticals in formation at large cluster-centric distances
- #bright SMGs at large radius could be an indication of final mass scale of cluster?
 - S850~8mJy SMGs indicate $\sim 10^{12}$ to 10^{13} Msun DM haloes (clustering analysis of Hickox+2012 and Garcia-Vergara+2020)
 - HS1549 has vastly more mass at large cluster-centric radius than SSA22.

A survey for protoclusters in South Pole Telescope 2500 deg²

A sample of $z=4-7$ candidate protoclusters resolved from the **South Pole Telescope (SPT)** survey.

Vieira et al. 2013
Spilker et al. 2016
Wang et al. 2021

G.Wang+2021
 Overdensity of
 LABOCA satellites,
 and SPIRE colours
 consistent with PC
 redshift.

Example: the star-forming protocluster SPT2349-56 at $z=4.3$

SPT2349-56 is the brightest SPT protocluster, with a 110mJy LABOCA source and central SFR well over 10,000 M_{\odot}/yr .

Miller et al. 2018

Rennehan et al. 2021

Rotermund et al. 2021

Hill et al. 2020,2022

Chapman et al. 2023

Most of central SMGs seem destined to rapidly merge into a BCG

Ultra-Deep Cycle 8 SPT2349-56 data

Now 35 [CII]- and continuum- detected galaxies at the protocluster redshift.

Deep Cycle 8 SPT2349-56 data

Far-infrared luminosity function best fit by power law, [CII] luminosity function best fit by Schechter function.

Of interest:

- Cross-correlate lower SNR sources with HST to go even deeper.
- Compare far-infrared/[CII] luminosity function to UV luminosity function.

Fainter [CI]1-0 than field,
 larger [CI]2-1/[CI]1-0
 than field
 ... **First discovery of
 environmental
 difference in SPT2349
 galaxies!**

Less molecular gas in SPT2349 than field?

- Different ISM conditions than field (Q₁₀ and X_{[CI])?}
- Used up cool gas supply? (more likely to have used up supplies in dense environment?)
- Blown away from outflows / shocks? (half of gas ends up in ICM / CGM from sims)

[CI] in SPT2349

(Chayce Hughes + in prep)

Are any of these SPT sources actually protoclusters?!?

- SPT2349 is awesome! But still lacking proof of the massive extended collapsing structure (LAE NB map with Magellan now exists ... TBD)
- SPT0457 and SPT2052 (both $z \sim 4$) have largest SMG count after 2349 and LBG analysis shows stronger overdensity than SPT2349
 - SPT0457 has 2 satellite LABOCA sources at $z=3.98$!
- SPT0303 Three structures in projection at $z=3-4$
- Remaining four (SPT0348, SPT0553, SPT2335, SPT0311) at $z > 5$ are currently just very bright/multiple SMGs (Hill+in prep)

All are in need of detailed, wide field, multi-wave study to understand PC environment

LBGs at
 $z \sim 4$:
 SPT0457
 (SPT2052
 similar)

*SPT0457 and SPT2052
 show **larger** LBG
 overdensities than
 SPT2349!*

SPT2052 and SPT0457 $z \sim 4.3$ protoclusters

Less multiplicity in faint SMGs than SPT2349

Not surprising that handful of bright SMGs don't fully span a $1e13 M_{\text{sun}}$ virial mass halo

SPT0303 Sulzenauer, Weiss+in prep

Images: Laboca SNR — 4 & 5 σ contours — rms contours

Extended core and incredible satellite SMG overdensity

**3 structures in projection
z=2.8, 3.2, 4.6**

ALMA follow-up: others shows projected secondary structures (red)

Hill+in prep

Conclusions

$z=3$ wide field SMGs in protoclusters

- Large variation in SMGs tracing extended 30' collapsing PC structure
- Bright SMGs are massive ellipticals in formation at large cluster-centric distances
- #bright SMGs at large radius an indication of final mass scale of cluster?

PCs found by unlensed SPT-SMGs at $z>4$

- Bright submm cores rapidly forming central BCG
- Signpost less active protocluster surroundings
- Often projected structures/SMGs contribute to SPT beam
- More work required to characterize protocluster environments

END